

Carbon-Nitrogen-Sulphur Relationships in Soils of West Bengal

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Carbon, nitrogen and sulphur relationships were studied in twelve profiles from five soil zones of West Bengal. Considerable variability in C : N, C : S, N : S and C : N : S ratios were observed in soils of different regions. Mean C : S and N : S ratios of the soil increased in the order: Coastal Saline < Lateritic < Alluvial < Hill < Terai. N : S ratio of surface soils were higher than the sub-surface layers. Presence of variable proportion of different components of organic matter in the soil under the influence of different climatic factors is suggested.

MOST of the sulphur, nitrogen and carbon in arable soils are present in organic forms. However, the importance of sulphur was overlooked in the earlier periods because of its incidental application as a constituent along with nitrogenous and phosphatic fertilizers. But the increased use of high analysis sulphur-free fertilizers, decreased use of sulphur as pesticides, introduction of high yielding varieties of crops which means greater requirement of all essential nutrients and decreased contribution of sulphur from atmospheric sources as a result of comparatively less combustion of sulphur containing fuels resulted in reports of more frequent and widespread sulphur deficiency in soils.

Considerable work has been done on the distribution of sulphur and its relationship with carbon and nitrogen in organic fraction in soils of many other states of India (Kanwar and Mohan¹, Kanwar and Takkar², Ahamed and Jha³, Venkateswarlu *et al*⁴, Virmani and Kanwar⁵, Bhan and Tripathi⁶ and Kumar and Singh⁷). But inspite of the reported deficiency of sulphur in soils of West Bengal (Dutta^{8,9}) so far no systematic effort on this aspect has been made on soils of this state. Moreover, most of the previous works on sulphur of different regions of India have been limited to surface soils and not in the zone of root penetration. This knowledge is obviously important for interpreting soil tests and fertilizer response to sulphur by deep rooting crops. The present paper therefore reports an examination of the vertical distribution of organic sulphur and its relationship with organic carbon and total nitrogen in soils of different regions of West Bengal.

Experimental

Twelve soil profiles from five regions (namely, Hill, Terai, Lateritic, Alluvial and Coastal Saline) of West Bengal were selected for the present investigation. Soils were collected from three different

depths viz., 0-15 cm, 15-30 cm and 30-45 cm layer in each profile. Samples were air-dried and crushed to pass through 0.5 mm sieve.

In the soil analyses reported (Table 1) pH was determined with a glass electrode pH meter (Soil : Water 1 : 2.5), organic carbon by wet digestion method of Walkely and Black (Jackson¹⁰) and total nitrogen by a semi-micro Kjeldahl method (Bremner¹¹). Total sulphur was determined by the method of Bardsley and Lancaster¹² and organic sulphur was calculated by subtracting inorganic sulphur from total sulphur. The concentrations of sulphur in the extracts were determined by the reduction method of Johnson and Nishita¹³.

Results and Discussion

Organic carbon, total nitrogen and organic sulphur contents in the soils (Table 1) and computed C : N, C : S, N : S and C : N : S ratios are presented in Table 2. The data presented in Table 1

TABLE 1—ANALYSES OF SOIL PROFILE SAMPLES

Region	Place of collection	Depth (cm)	pH	%Org. Carbon	%Total Nitrogen	%Org. Sulphur
	Ambutia, Kerseung	0-15	4.35	3.20	0.416	0.0256
		15-30	4.25	1.57	0.210	0.0212
		30-45	4.10	2.06	0.290	0.0206
Hill	Mundabasti, Darjeeling	0-15	4.90	3.14	0.424	0.0218
		15-30	4.85	2.59	0.334	0.0211
		30-45	4.70	2.27	0.330	0.0198
	Kalimpong	0-15	5.80	2.23	0.212	0.0178
		15-30	5.65	1.45	0.158	0.0115
		30-45	5.65	1.27	0.138	0.0110
Terai	Ektiasal, Jalpaiguri	0-15	5.15	2.28	0.258	0.0107
		15-30	5.65	1.80	0.219	0.0105
		30-45	5.40	1.20	0.156	0.0069
	Mohitnagar	0-15	5.50	2.33	0.281	0.0162
		15-30	5.20	2.32	0.236	0.0164
		30-45	5.20	2.69	0.224	0.0165

(Table 1 Contd.)

Lateritic	Raghunathpur	0-15	5.05	0.69	0.068	0.0091
		15-30	5.50	0.27	0.021	0.0053
		30-45	6.95	0.08	0.005	0.0018
	Sreeniketan	0-15	5.85	0.23	0.024	0.0044
		15-30	5.55	0.21	0.019	0.0045
		30-45	5.50	0.09	0.003	0.0024
Alluvial	Burdwan	0-15	6.05	0.36	0.037	0.0063
		15-30	6.95	0.27	0.025	0.0095
		30-45	6.70	0.10	0.009	0.0031
	Chinsurah	0-15	6.00	0.77	0.071	0.0050
		15-30	7.60	0.42	0.037	0.0051
		30-45	8.43	0.17	0.014	0.0030
	Mondouri	0-15	6.10	0.86	0.089	0.0084
		15-30	6.50	0.41	0.042	0.0045
		30-45	7.20	0.45	0.058	0.0072
Coastal Saline	Mathurapur	0-15	5.70	0.54	0.053	0.0081
		15-30	7.00	0.40	0.036	0.0066
		30-45	7.62	0.33	0.032	0.0064
	Canning	0-15	7.45	0.73	0.077	0.0116
		15-30	8.10	0.49	0.047	0.0120
		30-45	8.10	0.46	0.047	0.0073

TABLE 2—CARBON, NITROGEN AND SULPHUR RELATIONSHIPS IN SOILS

Region	Place of collection	Depth (cm)	C : N	N : S	C : S	C : N : S
Hill	Ambutia, Kerseung	0-15	7.7	16.2	125.1	77 : 10 : 0.61
		15-30	7.4	9.9	74.4	74 : 10 : 1.00
		30-45	7.1	14.1	99.9	71 : 10 : 0.71
	Mundabasti, Darjeeling	0-15	7.4	19.4	144.0	74 : 10 : 0.51
		15-30	7.7	15.8	122.7	77 : 10 : 0.63
		30-45	6.9	16.6	114.6	69 : 10 : 0.60
Kalimpong	0-15	10.5	11.9	126.0	105 : 10 : 0.83	
	15-30	9.1	10.2	93.6	91 : 10 : 0.98	
	30-45	9.2	12.5	115.4	92 : 10 : 0.80	
Mean		7.8	14.5	114.0	78 : 10 : 0.68	
Terai	Mohitnagar	0-15	8.3	17.3	143.8	83 : 10 : 0.57
		15-30	9.8	14.4	141.4	93 : 10 : 0.70
		30-45	12.0	13.5	163.2	120 : 10 : 0.73
	Ektiasal, Siliguri	0-15	8.8	24.1	213.6	88 : 10 : 0.41
		15-30	8.2	20.8	171.9	82 : 10 : 0.48
		30-45	7.7	22.6	292.6	77 : 10 : 0.26
Mean		9.2	17.9	164.0	92 : 10 : 0.54	
Lateritic	Raghunathpur	0-15	10.1	8.4	85.3	101 : 10 : 1.10
		15-30	12.8	3.9	50.9	128 : 10 : 2.50
		30-45	12.7	3.6	46.4	127 : 10 : 2.70
	Sriniketan	0-15	9.7	5.4	52.9	97 : 10 : 1.80
		15-30	11.1	4.2	47.1	111 : 10 : 2.30
		30-45	10.3	3.5	40.0	103 : 10 : 2.85
Mean		10.7	5.5	59.4	107 : 10 : 1.81	
Alluvial	Burdwan	0-15	9.8	5.9	57.6	98 : 10 : 1.70
		15-30	11.0	2.6	29.6	110 : 10 : 3.70
		30-45	11.8	2.9	33.9	118 : 10 : 3.40
	Chinsurah	0-15	10.9	14.5	157.9	109 : 10 : 0.69
		15-30	11.4	7.2	83.1	114 : 10 : 1.37
		30-45	12.3	4.6	57.6	123 : 10 : 2.14
Mondouri	0-15	9.7	10.7	103.7	97 : 10 : 0.93	
	15-30	9.7	9.5	92.7	97 : 10 : 1.04	
	30-45	7.8	8.0	63.3	78 : 10 : 1.24	
Mean		10.0	7.4	73.4	100 : 10 : 1.36	
Coastal Saline	Mathurapur	0-15	10.2	6.6	68.0	102 : 10 : 1.50
		15-30	11.1	5.4	60.4	111 : 10 : 1.83
		30-45	10.3	5.0	52.3	103 : 10 : 1.96
	Canning	0-15	9.4	6.6	63.3	94 : 10 : 1.50
		15-30	10.4	3.9	41.1	104 : 10 : 2.53
		30-45	9.9	6.3	62.7	99 : 10 : 1.59
Mean		10.1	5.6	56.4	101 : 10 : 1.78	
12 surface soils		0-15	8.6	14.0	120.9	86 : 10 : 0.71
36 soils		0-45	8.9	11.9	106.2	89 : 10 : 0.81

reveal that organic sulphur content of the surface horizons of the soil profiles examined varied from 18 to 256.7 ppm. Average organic sulphur content of Hill and Terai regions (189.6 and 124.3 ppm respectively) was noticeably higher than that observed in soils of Lateritic, Alluvial and Coastal Saline regions (average being 44.27, 57.81 and 86.85 ppm respectively). This was so because the organic matter contents of the soil profile of Hill and Terai region were higher than those of the other regions. It is also evident that the sulphur content showed a general decline with depth in the case of soils of acidic and neutral reaction, whereas, in soils of alkaline reaction no such regular decrease in sulphur content was observed. This is due to the fact that most of the soil sulphur present in neutral and acidic soils is primarily organic in nature. While in the case of saline soils the non-organic forms dominate (Mukhopadhyay and Mukhopadhyay¹⁴). But for the soils of Coastal Saline region, the organic sulphur decreased with depth. Organic matter also decreased with depth. Consequently organic sulphur which is also a constituent of soil organic matter also decreases. Similar trends were also reported by Venkateswarlu *et al*⁴.

The organic carbon to total nitrogen values for the fairly non-calcareous soils fall in the range of 7.1 to 12.8. These differences show little relationship with the present pH but they are readily understood on the basis that the C : N ratio indicates the degree of decomposition of organic matter. Other factors such as texture, altitude, relative freedom from drainage and differences in agricultural and manurial practice are doubtless also involved and contribute to the variations within groups. Considerable variability was observed in both C : S and N : S ratios of the soils collected from different regions (Table 2). It can be seen (Table 2) that while there is appreciable amount of variability within each region, mean C : S ratios of soil increased in the following order : Coastal Saline (56.8) < Lateritic (59.4) < Alluvial (73.4) < Hill (114.0) < Terai (164.0). The mean N : S ratios also increased in the soil following almost the same order as the mean C : S ratio : Lateritic (5 : 5) < Coastal Saline (5.6) < Alluvial (7.4) < Hill (14.5) < Terai (17.9). On a broader scale, the average N : S ratio for Hill and Terai regions was 16.2 whereas, that of plains was only 6.12. Organic matter of the acidic soils of semi temperate to temperate regions of Himalayan Hill and Terai are in a less decomposed state than in the plains. C : S, N : S ratio further indicate that the ratio of surface soils of all the twelve profiles were higher than those of the subsurface layers. This could result from difference in the nature of the organic matter itself. Similar observations were also reported by Virmani and Kanwar⁵. This explanation is partly confirmed by the studies of Williams and Steinbergs¹⁵ who observed that organic matter varied in nature at various depths in soils. Although more detailed information on the nature and distribution of such

compounds in different soils and their relationships with soil properties is necessary to clarify this aspect, it is clear that carbon, nitrogen and sulphur are closely associated in the soil as organic matter (Fig. 1) and it seems possible that the proportions may be defined within moderately narrow limits by microbial decomposition.

Fig. 1. Distribution of Organic Carbon, Total Nitrogen and Organic Sulphur among the Soil Zones
Organic C. $\times 1$ O—O Total N. $\times 10$ ●—● Organic S. $\times 100$ ▲—▲

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